

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND RESEARCH OF INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCES IN THE DIRECTION OF MONITORING THE QUALITY OF SCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In this article, an analysis of the literature on monitoring the quality of education in general education schools, a study of experiences in international general education institutions. Aimed at further improving the step-by-step implementation of international experiences in the establishment of quality education.*

Keywords: *research, international experience, scientific activity, potential personnel, young aspects of students.*

The main research on monitoring began in the 90s of the last century. To them V.I. Andreev, V.P. Bepalkov, V.A. The work done by Kalniy and others can be cited. In their work, Yu.V. Vasiliev, Yu.A. Konarzhevsky, V.S. Lezerov, T.I. They relied on the theoretical foundations of educational management created by Shamov et al. The work of these scientists was based on the development of the monitoring system - the content of management activities, management functions and principles were revealed. Over the next few years, issues directly related to the quality of education are being researched. Its technology and control mechanism are being developed. Including; D.Sh. Matros, D.M. Polev, N.N. Melenkova, N.A. Kulemin's works are dedicated to quality management of education based on monitoring.

Educational testing service has existed in the USA for half a century. Its mission is to generalize and expand testing practices, collect and analyze diagnostic data about students, and develop and test standardized tests. This service defines the rules for testing and monitors its implementation. It is located in the center of the university in Princeton and employs 2,300 people. In the 1970s, 150 of the employees were doctors of science and 200 were ministers of various educational subjects and other philosophy, pedagogy, psychology and statistics. This service has more than 5,000 testing points across the country. In the US, tests play an important role in higher education.

In the West, testing is used not only in educational institutions, but also to determine the educational level of young people working in enterprises. For example, in 1966, the Chamber of Commerce and Industry in Germany conducted such a test on more than 2,000 young people who had graduated in previous years and were working in enterprises. The results show that one in five has an unsatisfactory grade in writing, one in six can complete all four operations, and one in four has an unsatisfactory grade in arithmetic. In Europe, the tests are not as strong as in the US.

In England, public schools teach the course "Labor Education for Vocational Skills". During weekly compulsory lessons (1-2 hours), students fill out various tests and questionnaires. They are all done on computers.

In Egypt, according to the decision adopted in 1968, monthly oral and written tests are conducted in all subjects in the first three primary grades. At the end of the academic year, they are transferred to the next class based on their average grade. In the first three elementary grades,

monthly oral and written tests are conducted in all subjects. At the end of the academic year, they are transferred to the next class based on their average grade. Even in the Republic of Chad, in the early 70s, the selection for grades 4-6 was made through tests. Tests are widely used in Turkey. It has a test center similar to the one in the US. There are also test centers in the Baltic Republic, Russia and Uzbekistan.

At the 10-year meeting (2005) on the place of education in sustainable development at the United Nations, many issues that are waiting for their solution in many countries were put before the leaders of the countries. But improving the quality of education can only be successful if there is a need for society, and not something forced from above. Currently, four countries that have made great progress in improving the quality of education can be cited: Finland (the economic crisis of 1990 led to the development of a strategy for the development of a knowledge-based economy);

Canada (education is an important key in nation-building (lots of immigrants)); Cuba (education meets the goals and values of community development). Korea initially achieved quantitative growth, but later began to focus on quality from the 1980s. A separate tax was introduced for the development of education. Scientific research institutes lead the referendums. In 1990, a consultative body was established to support reforms independent of the government. The reform is widely supported. According to the conducted international studies (PISA), Korea currently ranks first in science, third in mathematics, and seventh in reading.

In Cuba, education is considered in the direction of strengthening the role in the harmonious development of the individual (physical education takes on sports, artistic education). Currently, investment in education in Cuba is 11% of GDP. Illiteracy has dropped from 40% to zero.

Teaching is one of the most prestigious professions in Canada. The competition among those wishing to study in the field of pedagogy is very large. A teacher is required to study for 40 days per year without leaving work, and it is funded. They are obliged to undergo certification every five years. Educators who have not passed certification will lose their teaching certificate. Monitoring of the quality of education is carried out annually at the school, district and regional levels. Canada ranks second in reading, seventh in math and sixth in science. Interestingly, the children of immigrants showed a higher level than the native children.

Finland ranks first in reading, fifth in math and fourth in science. It led to the creation of the same conditions for study everywhere and the development of the entire society and the entire economy. Achieving high student performance while not spending much on education has led to great success in 15 years. Each teacher has a master's degree in two subjects.

It should be noted that in the Republic of Uzbekistan, teachers and trainers are considered to be prestigious professions. The majority of applicants who want to enter higher educational institutions have applied to higher educational institutions in the field of pedagogy. The analysis of scientific literature shows that the quality of education is assessed mainly according to the results of the approach to the mentioned problems. In this, the main place is allocated to their cognitive aspects. The obtained results do not take into account the conditions created in the educational institution, the organization of the educational process. The activity of many schools was determined by the number of students from this school, the places they got in science olympiads and sports competitions, how many teachers there were, and how much money the school had in its account. Such data give only quantitative indicators and do not allow an objective

assessment of the quality of education. Accordingly, it is impossible to predict the future and make clear plans for improving the quality of education. Studies have shown that the concept of "Educational quality" itself is not sufficiently scientifically defined. Accordingly, a contradiction arose between the uncertainty of the pedagogical interpretation of the new quality level in education and its provision according to social requirements. That is, the existence of a conflict between the need to control the fulfillment of the social order for quality education and the incomplete development of the criteria and mechanism of its objective evaluation shows the existence of a problem of the mechanism of ensuring the effective management of the educational system by means of theoretical justification of the quality of school education and its monitoring.

In general, there is no participation of international programs in the evaluation and monitoring of the education system in our country, or there is no "National Program" for evaluating or monitoring the level of knowledge of students, determining the quality of mastery of one or another subject by young people in the region and the scope of work that should be carried out in the field. and is limiting the possibility of carrying out relevant reforms. Also, the fact that the level of teaching in primary and general secondary educational institutions lags behind the pace of reforms will cause a shortage of qualified personnel in the near future. Taking this into account, we consider it permissible to make the following suggestions: To thoroughly study the issue of Uzbekistan's participation in international education quality assessment programs and ensure participation in these programs;

- Creation of the "National program" of assessment or monitoring of the level of knowledge of students based on international experience;
- Considering the most advanced results of scientific achievements and the publication of literature in English, considering the issue of implementing various foreign programs that teach English;
- To determine the qualification requirements of specialists responsible for education in preschool educational institutions through specific criteria and to establish by law the full responsibility of children in general education;
- Setting the maximum and minimum indicators of the number of students in groups and classes of preschool education and general secondary education institutions, based on methods tested in international experience;
- Establishing specialized classes for 8-9-year-olds in each school, separating gifted children from primary classes with the help of psychological tests.

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